

IMPACT OF VARIOUS FACTORS ON STRUCTURAL CHANGES OF AGRICULTURE SECTOR – A CASE STUDY OF UTTARKASHI

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ABSTRACT

The Uttarakhand state is one of a great example of structural changes, traditional agriculture and crops, from last five years Uttarakhand state passes with the big natural and climatically Disaster we can say that the natures give some agonizing wound to the Uttarakhand state especially to the Uttarkashi district faced regular and heavy flood in 1978, 1997 and 1998, mass land slide in Varunawat hill in 2003 and onwards the biggest one of 2009 and 2013 disaster It will take years to roll back the physical, psychological, social, economic and ecological damage wrought by the terrible floods in Uttarakhand, which killed more than 1,000 people. Thus the possibility of earthquake, flood and landslides are always occurring there. In Garhwal Himalayan Mountains landslide and earthquake have been major and widely spread that strike life and property almost perennially year after year. Uttarakhand state and especially Uttarkashi district is facing the regular disaster from 1978, 1988, 1991, 1997-1998 and mass land slide in Varunawat hill in 2003-2006, 2009, 2010 and onwards the biggest disaster and deluge one of 2012 and 2013 disaster but local state government didn't learn a lesson from these disaster and a small compensation is given to affected peoples of the region and no concrete steps are taken to repair the affected roads and houses, and this has been don from the past many years. The deeper causes of this epic tragedy were natural and but manmade. They ensured that cloudbursts and heavy rainfall, which routinely occur in Uttarakhand upper hills, turned into a catastrophe after that and as research point of view Uttarkashi and Uttarakhand needs the revival strategy of the development in each section. In this backdrop the current research endeavor is entitled to study.

Keywords: Agribusiness, ANOVA, Disaster, Uttrakhand, India, Mountain, Glacier, Floods

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is a critical sector of the Indian economy. It forms the backbone of development in the country. An average Indian still spends almost half of his/her total expenditure on food, while roughly half of India's work force is still engaged in agriculture for its livelihood. Agriculture is a source of livelihood and food security for a vast majority of low income, poor and vulnerable sections of society. Given that India is still home to the largest number of poor and malnourished people in the world, a higher priority to agriculture will

achieve the goals of reducing poverty and malnutrition as well as of inclusive growth. Since agriculture forms the source base for a number of agro-based industries and agro-services, it would be more meaningful to view agriculture not as farming alone but as a holistic value chain, which includes farming, wholesaling, warehousing (including logistics), processing, and retailing. Further, it may be noted that in the last two Five Year Plans, it is clearly mentioned that for the economy to grow at 9 per cent, it is important that agriculture should grow at least by 4 per cent per annum.

Structural change of a country mainly refers to changes in the output structure and changes in the occupation structure of a country. Output structure means composition of national output, i.e., contribution to national income by different sectors of an economy, namely, primary, secondary and tertiary sectors. The occupation structure means composition of labour-force according to different occupations, i.e., in the three different sectors of the economy. Thus, while structural change includes changes in both production and employment structures, changes in occupation structure embraces only the changes in employment structure. Economists have shown an important statistical relation between the production and occupation structures of a country and the degree of its economic development. Colin Clark in his pioneering study, "The Conditions of Economic Progress", comments:

" as time goes on and communities become more economically advanced, the numbers engaged in agriculture tend to decline relative to the numbers in manufacture, which, in their turn, decline relative to the numbers engaged in services". (Clark, 1957, p.492)."

Structural change in agriculture (or any sector) is characterized by constant changes in the deployment of the production factors of labour (including human capital), land and financial capital. Social capital in the form of social networks is a resource, not to say a production factor, that appears to be more and more important in the economic and thus the structural adjustment process of economic sectors, notably also in the agricultural sector. Structural change manifests itself in a clear change in the structure of production.

Within agriculture, the size of the workforce and the number of farms are reduced, often to the benefit of a relatively higher number of larger farms. In relation to the national economy, the proportion of those employed in agriculture falls.

Nevertheless, while the primary agricultural sector seems to be sometimes in a deadlock, the up- and downstream enterprises (including wholesale and retail) associated to the agricultural sector appear to be more dynamic. In this context, vertically integrated food production may more easily generate structural change than independent farming.

Growth, especially uneven growth in the different sectors of an economy automatically produces structural change. Productivity growth in a sector not only causes economic growth but results in sectoral and inter-sectoral shifts of employment. While economic growth is positive, labour shifts may be associated – at least temporarily – with social hardship. This seems to be frequently the case in structural adjustment processes in agriculture. One could observe this in the first phase of structural change, when state owned, corporate and cooperative farms were broken apart within the privatization process of transition and in a more recent phase

when the many small-scale farms that were a result of the transition process found themselves incapable of generating a inter-regionally comparable livelihood base. If farms see a potential for growth, they invest in the adoption of new technologies to increase agricultural productivity and thus improve their livelihoods. Nevertheless, larger farms tend to switch more easily to new technologies. This may be due to better capital availability or a higher degree of managerial capability. The managerial capability is also crucial for the adaptive.

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RISK ASSESSMENT

(I) Floods and Landslides: - Vast area of the district are prone to having landslides and flash flood, particularly during the raining season due to heavy rain or sudden cloudburst. Such incidents have often been witnessed in the past at place Joshiyara, Gangori, Gyansu, Mori, Dharasu Sand Agora and in the river Indravati, Bhagirathi, Yamuna. Similarly, because of loose structure of soil in the mountain range along the banks of river Ganga and Yamuna, there is always a possibility of heavy landslides in the area. The river at this place is about 20-30 feet wide and sudden landslides can obstruct the flow or river Ganga and Yamuna resulting in a flood like situation in the upper parts of the area.

(II) Earthquake: - As mentioned that the district is located in the most sensitive seismic zone of the Himalaya and the main center thrust and the main boundary thrust lines are passing through the district, the possibility of the district being rocked by an earthquake is inevitable.

(III) Road Accident: - The area being hilly, road accident like vehicles falling into the river or deep gorges may be due to worst condition or roads, land sliding, mechanical failure, overspending or overtaking, often take place.

(IV) Fires: - Almost 85% of the total area of the district is covered by forest. During the binging summers forest fires have often taken place in the past resulting in loss of animal life and vegetation

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A detailed Literature has been reviewed to make the study relevant. Few key observations obtained from Literature cited are elaborated below:

S. No	Authors	Year	Objectives of Study	Key Observations
1.	S.S. Acharya	2007	The study focuses on Agribusiness in India and its main objective was to scientifically analyse Agribusiness that should lead to carving out a path out of poverty, food insecurity and malnutrition for all those who have waited enough, in the shortest possible time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> From the study it was found that despite several forms of government intervention and a number of marketing development programmes, the marketing system for farm products has continued to suffer from several weaknesses. The farmers have borne the brunt of these weaknesses. The private sector, for long, did not invest or shied away from investment in the agricultural marketing activities. It is only during the past five years or so, i.e. the second phase of liberalization, that the agricultural marketing reforms were initiated.
2.	R.K. Maikhuri, L.S. Rawat , R.L. Semwal, K.S. Rao And K.G. Saxena	2015	The objective of the paper was to provide an overview of organic agriculture programmes that have been attempted in Uttarakhand state of India. Much of the rural land in India, especially in Himalaya is fragmented and the problems created by male outmigration coupled with market forces influence the viability of the future farming in the region.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This paper identified the key problems, their causes and the scope of solutions based on the perceptions of the farmers participating in the organic farming training and development. The present approach of providing subsidy as part of policy though encourages the farmers to take up the programmes, they need to build the capacity to continue the organic farming once the subsidy is withdrawn.
3.	Shoji Lal Bairwa And Udhav Prasad Singh	2015	This paper tried to explore the opportunities and challenges of agribusiness sector in the country.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to the research there is no doubt that agribusiness industry has a lot of potential to improve rural incomes and can play a very significant role in creation of employment for rural youths. The present study focused on the need to critically look at how can people get the opportunities and how can alleviate the constraints faced by the agribusiness sector in the country.
4.	H. Ramakrishna	2012	The objectives of the study were: 1. To know the business environment for private sector to take part in research related agricultural activities. 2. To analyze the wave of FDI in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The study analyzed Integrated Agribusiness Development Policy developed by Karnataka government to cover agriculture and allied sectors.

			agriculture 3. To understand the options available for private investment in the newly introduced Integrated Agribusiness Development Policy (IADP) 2011 of the Government of Karnataka	
5.	Vasant P. Gandhi	2014	The study tries to find out the importance of agribusiness and the transformation happened over the years.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study explained that there has been substantial growth and transformation of the agribusiness sector in India. • The transformation of agribusiness in developing countries such as in India appears to be driven by significant constraints, demands, and shifts that occur in the economy as development proceeds. Author made an effort to identify some of the important shifts and constraints that emerge, and the impact they generate and will continue to have on agriculture and agribusiness development. This is important not only to understand what the origins and causes of agribusiness growth are, but also the likely direction of future changes.
6.	Raghavendra Hajgolkar, Talwar Sabanna	2017	The present study is based on the following objectives: 1. To study the overview opportunities for entrepreneurs that exists in agribusiness in India. 2. To examine the scope for agribusiness in India and reasons for low rate of success in agribusiness. 3. To study the challenges and growth opportunities for entrepreneurs in agribusiness. 4. To assess the strategy for promotion of successful enterprises in agriculture sector in India.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to the study Agribusiness enterprises at the local level offer the possibility of capturing value added and thereby increasing local incomes. Since many smallholders have relied on government buyers for their marketing options, the retraction of those services is un-likely to be immediately replaced by private enterprise. Also, even when such services are available, small producers do not present as attractive a transaction to service providers because of the often enormous costs of transacting with many small clients.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

(a) IMPACT OF VARIOUS FACTORS ON STRUCTURAL CHANGES OF AGRICULTURE SECTOR IN STUDY AREA UTTARKASHI

Mountains are amongst the most fragile environments in the world and are a repository of biodiversity, water and other ecosystem services. Mountains influence far more than their geographical limits and extend to the surrounding lowlands with the goods and services. The mountains are facing enormous pressures from various global change related driving forces including land use change. The land use change is happening in an unprecedented manner in the

Himalaya. FAO (1992) defines land as an area of the earth's surface, including all elements of the physical environment that influence land use. Thus land refers not only to soil but also landforms, climate and hydrology, plant and animal population, and the physical results of human activity like terraces and drainage works.

In a general way, land use is any kind of permanent or cyclic human intervention to satisfy human needs, either material or spiritual or both, from the complex of natural and artificial resources which together are called "land". Contemporary earth scientists opine - land carries ecosystems; land use is the application of human controls, in a relatively systematic manner, to the key elements within any ecosystems, in order to harness benefit from it. The concept of land use is a wide and complex and has different meaning in different aspects. The effect of terrain conditions on land use pattern may be considered as direct, which set the foundation of land use and ultimately reflected in their spatial variations over different components of landform. Different terrain conditions like altitude, relief measures, slope morphology, drainage aspects etc. have significant role in the pattern on land use. This section of the chapter presents a systematic and scientific approach to analysis of the structural changes and agricultural land use pattern of the Uttarkashi area. Utilization of land for different purposes is governed by physical as well as socio-economic characteristics such as altitude, relief and slope, soil characteristics, irrigation facilities, diversification of economy, transport etc. of the area under study.

IDENTIFICATION OF LAND USE PATTERNS:

Based on the altitudinal variation and land utilization characteristics, some important land use patterns have been identified with the help of intensive field study, topographical maps and satellite imagery (LISS m, 1998 & 2005 and also LISS IV, 2005) with the help of remote sensing and GIS techniques. The researcher has been analyzed the village level land use pattern with the G.P.S survey and also with the Census data. On the other hand, for the remote sensing approach the satellite image of Uttarkashi-Gangotri area collected from NE.SC, Hyderabad, Govt, of India and this image refers to the digital data of LISS HI (Nov, 1997 & Nov, 2005) and LISS IV (Nov, 2005) identified and analyzed the land use patterns with the GIS techniques using Erdas and Arc GIS Software followed by ground verification.

The land use of the Uttarkashi area has been largely influenced by the nature of the Himalayan mountainous terrain and the diversity of the climate particularly the variations in precipitation and soils. The identified land use pattern of the area registered eleven categories i.e.

- 1) Forest,
- 2) Degraded forest,
- 3) Agricultural land,
- 4) Built up area,
- 5) River sand, 6) Road
- 7) Snow covered area,

- 8) Water body,
- 9) Barren land (rocky),
- 10) Hilly area with out forest
- 11) Scrab land or grass land

Worldwide, flash floods and landslides have always scared us as swift and stealthy killers. These often attack without any premonition and give no time to respond. Landslides, too, bury more than 5000 people alive every year globally, along with economic losses of over 4 billion USD.

These are one of the worst forms of natural disasters that humanity has experienced. But just fearing them alone won't help, one needs to understand them and learn how to deal with these disasters. The present document is an attempt to highlight the lessons learnt from the landslide and flash flood disaster that hit a part of the Uttarkashi district in the Upper Bhagirathi Valley of Garhwal Himalaya during the first week of August 2012.

On the unfortunate night of Friday, 3rd August 2012 at about 10pm, the upper catchment areas of Asi Ganga and Bhagirathi rivers received very heavy (64.5 – 124.4mm) rainfall/cloudburst accompanied with thunderstorms and lightning. The atmospheric phenomena was followed by blocked drainage channels due to tree logs, sediments and boulders resulting in damming of water channels and formation of transient lakes in some tributaries of Asi Ganga and Bhagirathi rivers.

These transient lakes bursted after a short span of damming and added large volumes of water, tree logs boulders and sediments into the Bhagirathi River. Not long ago, the area had received very heavy precipitation on the 4th and 25th July 2012 in the Asi Ganga valley and a transient dam was formed by debris material. Besides transient dams and lakes in these channels, the natural lakes like Dodi Tal on the upstream side were also full of water and even started overflowing. Asi Ganga basin is narrow and long with a large watershed area and is susceptible to flashfloods, landslides and debris flows. In comparison, the river Bhagirathi has a wide valley and is fed by numerous tributaries (including Asi Ganga) and glaciers. Both the Asi Ganga as well as Bhagirathi river were in high spate at the time of the tragedy.

The flash floods, landslides and debris flows during the night took away 34 human lives (who were sleeping unawakingly in their homes close to the river) and caused heavy destruction to buildings, infrastructures and projects located by riverside. Gangori and Swarigad both lying in Bhatwari Tehsil of Uttarkashi district, were cut-off from other areas due to washing away of roads by flash floods and landslides, and pilgrims were stranded on their trek from Gangotri to Uttarkashi. The torrential rains raised the water level in the Bhagirathi River by about 4m. The

consequent flash floods swept away people, livestock, bridges, roads, houses, some hydel projects, electric poles, water pipelines mainly along the banks of the rivers of Asi Ganga and Bhagirathi.

The fire station at Gangori was washed away by the flash floods claiming lives of 3 firemen/constables and damaging the building, equipment and vehicles of the fire station. The power plant on river Asi Ganga was also hit by the flash floods leading to loss of lives of 23 workers camping at the site. The bridge at Gangori was washed away, disrupting the traffic Gangori. The Tiloth bridge on the other side of the river Bhagirathi that connects the Uttarkashi city, also collapsed. Apart from that, many pedestrian bridges were also washed away. Roads were blocked due to landslides and collapse of bridges which resulted in pilgrims being stranded at Gangori, Bhatwari, Harsil and Chinyalisaur. In the twin disaster of flashfloods and landslides in the district, 28 people died and 6 went missing (who were also considered later as dead).

Agriculture and Irrigation in the Himalayan region, there are many constraints in the agriculture sector like the availability of cultivable land. It can be seen from the fact that as much as 88% of the area is either covered by forests or is barren and uncultivable. The land is poor in fertility, except in valleys and such land is too little and distantly placed. Shorter agricultural season, low temperatures, high altitude, small land holding, perpetual problems of soil erosion due to steep gradients etc., are other inhibiting factors affecting agriculture. It, therefore, does not offer too much hope for bringing about well being to the people of the area. Sheep rearing for wool and meat, orchard raising, spinning and weaving of wool and other cottage industries etc. offer much scope and their potential be exploited to the fullest extent. The cultivation in these areas are carried on largely by making terraces on the sloping hillsides, and sometimes cultivation is even done on steep hills also where terracing and tilling cannot be done and the place is cleared by burning scrubs and bushes. The seeds are sown with the help of a hoe. This practice of cultivation is known as 'Katil' and both Rabi as well as Kharif crops are harvested.

The main Kharif crops are paddy, small millets and potato and the Rabi crops are wheat and barley. These crops account for over 80 percent of the total cropped area. Horticulture is another field that could boost up the economy of the district. However, it has not made much headway due to difficulties in marketing the produce remoteness and poor communications setup.

4. CONCLUSION

Most of the villagers of study area in Uttarakashi district of Uttarakhand are directly and indirectly dependent on agricultural lands and cultivation for their livelihoods. There are non-agriculture based livelihoods, but they need special skills and technical knowhow. Sometimes, socio-cultural status of people also provides traditional sources of income. Though access to livelihoods resources and their ownership explain the vulnerability and capability of people (Chambers 1989; Kumar et al. 2009), dependence on these sources of livelihood is

important for understanding the level of vulnerability. Most of the poor families have low agricultural land holding and limited access to natural resource. Daily survival of these people is highly dependent on agricultural lands and other informal sources of livelihoods.

Therefore, impact of disaster is not only dependent on access to sources of livelihoods but also on the level of dependency on these sources of livelihoods. Most of the villagers depend on multiple sources of livelihoods which include agriculture, agricultural labour work, rickshaw pulling, earthwork, daily wage labour work, and seasonal migration. Those who depend only on one source of livelihood, face difficulties after to losing their sole sources of livelihood.

As the villagers are highly dependent on natural resources, they become vulnerable to disaster because of their limited ability to manage the situation (Flint and Luloff 2005:399). Therefore, farming families of Uttarkashi in chronic flood-affected villages are unable cope with crisis of livelihood.

Impact of flood on land owning families is not static. The impacts of chronic flood on these families cause reduction of their dependency on land. Though these families are able to access agricultural land, they have limited agricultural production to cope with disaster. As a result, chronic floods and river encroachment aggravate their vulnerability. The overall finding in this regard is that the disadvantaged groups of villagers are highly vulnerable to the loss of livelihood sources, but this does not mean that all people in disadvantaged communities are vulnerable to disaster.

It mainly depends on the livelihood strategies and their capabilities to reduce the impact of disaster.

Agriculture is the main source of livelihood of many villagers in flood-affected hamlets. Loss of agricultural livelihoods is caused by the loss of landmass, destruction of agricultural crops, lowering of agricultural productivity, and impossibility or non-viability of agricultural activities (see figure 6.1). Loss of agriculture based livelihoods have different impacts on affected villagers and it is dependent on extent of their involvement in agricultural production and distribution. The loss of agriculture livelihoods cause impact on sources of income, assets, and stocks of agricultural products and the skills and knowledge related to agricultural activities.

Our selective survey on classical economics-based researches on structural change, agriculture or agribusiness, and migration suggests that, overall, the empirical evidence supports the idea that Uttarkashi structural changes in agricultural productivity could represent an important mediating channel in the agriculture-migration relationship. In fact, the importance of

agriculture emerges from both plenty of micro-level country studies based on individual or household data and the few macro-level analyses using cross-sectional country data over longer time periods. Thus, policy actions targeted to sustainable agriculture and rural development can both help tackle the challenges posed by climate change and create opportunities in the face of growing internal and international migration

REFERENCES

- Afroz Alam, Aqeel Hasan Rizvi, Khushbu Verma, Chhaya Gautam. (2014). "The Changing Scenario in Indian Agriculture: A Review", *International Journal of Scientific Research in Agricultural Sciences*, Vol. 1(7), pp. 118-127
- Alfons Balmann, Kirsti Dautzenberg, Kathrin Happe and Konrad Kellermann. (2006). "On the dynamics of structural change in agriculture Internal frictions, policy threats and vertical integration", *Outlook on AGRICULTURE*, Vol 35, No 2, pp 115–121
- Alfons Balmann, Vladislav Valentinov. (2016). "Towards a Theory of Structural Change in Agriculture: Just Economics", *Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies*
- Atul Bansal. (2011). "Agri-Business in India – Vision 2020", *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol.1 Issue 2
- Avinash sharma, Monoj Sutradhar, Sheelawati Monlai and Nirupa Kumari. (2018). "Present and Past Status of Indian Agriculture", *Agricultural Research & Technology Open Access Journal*, Vol. 17, Issue 5
- B P Sharma. (2015). "Present Position of Agriculture in India", *International Journal of Science and Research*, Vol. 5, Issue 4
- Badar Alam Iqbal. (2018). "Indian Agricultural Scenario in 21st Century", *Journal of Food Science and Toxicology*, Vol. 2, No. 6
- Chandra Prakash Kala. (2014). "Changes in Traditional Agriculture Ecosystem in Rawain Valley of Uttarakhand State in India", *Applied Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp: 90-93
- Deepak Kumar Behera & Mitali Tiwari. (2011). "Structural Transformation in India: An Econometric Investigation"
- Dipti parkas Pal & Mausumi Datta Biswas. (2012). "The Changing Structure of Indian Agriculture during the Post-Reform Period: A Study in the IO Framework"
- Donn A. Reimund, Charles V. Moore and J. Rod Martin. (1977). "Factors Affecting Structural Change in Agricultural Subsectors: Implications for Research", *Southern Journal of Agricultural Economics*
- S.S. Acharya. (2007). "Agribusiness in India: Some Facts and Emerging Issues". *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, Vol. 20, pp: 409-424
- Shoji Lal Bairwa & Udhav Prasad Singh. (2015). "Development of agribusiness industry in India: opportunities, challenges and solutions", *International Journal of Commerce and Business Management*, Vol. 8, Issue 1, pp: 88-93

- Siba Sankar Mohanty & Atul Singh. (2014). “Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC) Act in Uttarakhand and its Impact on Agribusiness”, International Journal of Marketing and Technology, Vol. 4, Issue 4
- Sravanthi Kolla, Venu B. N & Umesh K. B. (2015). “The Structural Transformation of Indian Economy: A Critical Analysis”, International Journal of Agricultural Science and Research, Vol. 5, Issue 3, pp: 173-184
- Subhasankar Chattopadhyay. (2016). “Slow Structural Change in India: Is It Related to Rising Relative Price of Agriculture? A Partial Equilibrium Model”, Theoretical Economics Letters, Vol. 6, pp: 401-406
- Surajit Mazumdar. (2010). “Industry and services in growth and structural change in India: some unexplored features”, Institute for Studies in Industrial Development, MPRA Paper No. 20401
- Vasant P. Gandhi. (2014). “Growth and Transformation of the Agribusiness Sector: Drivers, Models and Challenges”, Ind. Jn. of Agri. Econ. Vol.69, No.1
- Vishwambhar Prasad Sati. (2005). “Systems of Agriculture Farming in the Uttranchal Himalaya, India, Journal of Mountain Science, Vol 2 No 1, pp: 76~85
- Vittorio Valli and Donatella Saccone. (2009). “Structural Change and Economic Development in China and India”, The European Journal of Comparative Economics Vol. 6, no.1, pp. 101-129